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The Socio-Cultural Meanings of the New Pedagogical Education

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Abstract

This article actualizes the problem of future teacher professional training in the terms of new pedagogical education; it reveals the methods of dynamic and contextual educational system analysis and theoretical analysis of scientific and special literature, which formulates social challenges to education, its new socio-cultural meanings; it also gives normative constructs of national educational policy, regulating and approving main directions of further national education development. The review presents the experience of foreign countries that achieved success in education (France, Finland, Germany, Poland) and the methodological bases of socio-cultural interaction between State and Society, according to the socio-cultural partnership principle and methodological approaches (culturological and humanitarian – culturological) for the formulated problem solution. It formulates conceptually and justifies essentially the definition of "socially active school" and "socially oriented education", which highlights the interrelated components – social and educational, that allows these phenomena to solve social and educational problems successfully and effectively. The article gives the analysis of future teacher professional competence and formulates the following labor functions: necessary skills and knowledge for the professional standard "Teacher", labor actions, it also gives the normative basis for new generation pedagogical shots training and intends for unified requirements establishment to the professional pedagogical activity maintenance and quality, for teachers' qualification level assessment; it presents different resources for new pedagogical education taking into account contemporary socio-cultural meanings (senses). The data broaden the theoretical idea of the teacher of the future professional training in the Russian education contemporary development and stimulate projecting new pedagogical education.

Key words: pedagogical education, socio-cultural situation, competence, professional standard.

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Introduction

The essential problem

Russian society is going through the period of deep fundamental, structural socio-cultural transformations both in society and education and socio - economic sphere, due to the search for new meanings.

In this regard, we cannot do without the innovation in education, which is naturally intensified in the program "Digital economics". At the same time, it becomes clear that it is no longer possible to avoid the present day challenges (Putin, 2017).

The current education development in Russia sets up new strategic tasks to its subjects for realizing the national project "Education" and its main federal projects "Contemporary school" and "The teacher of the future" in the terms of socially-oriented education. Hence, all citizens of Russia, the family and the parents' community, Federal and regional institutions of state power, local self-government bodies, the professional and pedagogical community, scientific, cultural, commercial, public institutions, etc. are called to become active subjects of educational policy.

Normative documents of the national educational policy: "Decree of the Prime Minister of the Russian Federation № 2620 R", "Changes in the sectors of social sphere aimed at improving the efficiency of education and science", "Education strategy in the Russian Federation for the period up to 2025", Priority projects: "Modern digital educational environment in the Russian Federation" and "Development of export potential of the Russian education system", decree Of the President of the Russian Federation may 7, 2018. № 204 "On national goals and strategic tasks of the Russian Federation development for the period up to 2024" regulate and approve the main directions of its further development — quality, availability, variability of educational services, digitalization, innovation, socio-cultural orientation for the individual needs of each person and all subjects of social education order.

The formulated thesis is a direct challenge to the universities implementing the program of pedagogical orientation, and a strong argument in favor of a professional teacher education reboot. In the current realities pedagogical universities are searching for new socio-cultural meanings of pedagogy, more and more improving innovative tools to choose their own trajectory for modern teachers training, taking into account the current socio-cultural situation (Yusupova, 2018).

Literature review

It becomes obvious that the processes of developing Russian education strategic prospects vision are extremely relevant but, at the same time, difficult without a comprehensive scientific improvement, in-depth analysis of existing positive experience, as well as a strategic forecast of the planned innovations results (Skudareva, 2015).

In a narrow sense, socio-cultural partnership is defined by scientists as the interaction of certain institutions or specialists, as a condition for the formation of certain personal qualities of students in a particular type of educational institutions, which narrows the essence of this type of partnership and, consequently, the possibility of its application in the process of active interaction between the state and society.

As noted by Milkevich (2017), the essence of social and cultural partnership as a multi-aspect concept can be represented in the aggregate of the following meanings: in a broad sense as a social

contract form for solving a particular problem, meeting the social needs of a group of people within a new system of relations, which has a certain cultural framework (values, norms, traditions); in a more narrow sense as a set of attitudes and actions of some subjects, which determine the willingness and ability for the decision of socially-significant problems through joint activities, pooling efforts and resources on the background of a clear awareness of responsibility; in a narrow sense as a direct interaction of some constituents (employees of education institutions, culture, representatives of public organizations, etc.) in the course of a socially significant problem (Milkevich, 2017).

Theoretical analysis of scientific literature defines the essence of socially active school (SAS) and socially oriented education in a conceptual way, especially as the SAS model in Russia is gaining more and more official recognition. The basis of the definition of Kornetov (2009), who described the socially active school "as a resource of its own development and itself as a resource of community development, its democratization, seeking to bring education as close as possible to the life of the child, to rely on the socializing potential of various social practices and based in its activities on the mechanisms of volunteerism and partnership" (Decker & Boo, 1996).

The foreign interpretation of the concept "socially-oriented education" (SOE) can be commonly recognized in Russia today. "Socially-oriented education is an educational philosophy that underlies the creativity of socially active schools, contributes to the creation of opportunities for members of the community-individuals, schools, business, public and private organizations – become partners in meeting the needs of the community to provide academic, recreational, health, social services and training programs for people of all ages" (Kornetov, 2009).

Of particular relevance in this case is the study of foreign countries experience that have achieved some success in education, in particular France, Finland, Germany, Poland, where it is possible to see and study in practice the specific features of education abroad, the problems and ways to solve them, affecting scientific and sociological research.

Thus, the system of education in Poland studied and summarized the integral characteristics of the Polish teacher professional activity in the field of psychological and pedagogical Sciences, which are of undoubted practical interest for the teacher's personality researchers and are reflected in his real professional activity (Kovalczuk–WaŁędziak, 2012).

German education system study reveals that the development of educational institutions network and various forms of ongoing education is one of the distinctive features of the German education. The vocational schools are especially numerous at various levels of training in the system of non-formal vocational education and training, as well as non-formal and informal education and teaching for adults (Klieger & Levinz, 2015).

Universities of France are engaged in scientific projects, so students carry out research on pedagogy, psychology, sociology, computer electronics, etc. Most of the research projects and creative laboratories are supported and funded by the French national center for scientific research and the National Institute of computer technology research (Belghith, 2015).

In comparison with other countries, Finland is a leader in the development of the information society in many respects. The new government is focused on digital education, respectively, in recent years, preference in funding was given to digital technologies, so that Finnish schools are more than sufficiently supplied with modern equipment. The experience of Finland is extremely interesting and important for us in terms of the effectiveness of educational reforms and the conditions for their implementation (New Learning Environment in Finland, 2016).

At the same time, the official document of the European Union "Specific future goals of vocational training and education systems" states: "while we must preserve the differences in structure and systems that reflect the originality of different countries and regions in Europe, we must also recognize that our main goals and results, to which we all aspire, are remarkably similar. We must rely on these similarities, learn from each other, share our successes and failures ... to advance our European citizens and European society in the new Millennium" (EU Documents, 2001).

Contemporary tendencies

This challenge to the Russian education system aims at the implementation of global educational brands in the current socio-cultural situation. Focusing on the foregoing, socio-cultural pedagogical mission of the University in future teacher of modern school professional training is the formation of Pedagogical University readiness to meet the challenges of state authority and society to combine efforts with all stakeholders to find answers to the questions addressed to the professional pedagogical education content, to understand them in order to determine the socio-cultural guidance of the future teacher preparation for the new public active school, which change its educational guidelines, role and status, the development of technologies for socio-cultural interaction with the community allows it to reach a new level, to become a unified beginning and a field for active socio-cultural interaction between the state and society.

Methodological basis

Hence, the research targets are:

- determination of the main positions of professional pedagogical education renewal, which solves the actual problem of a qualitative change in the preparation of the teacher of the future;
- identifying the methodological foundations of the state and society socio-cultural interaction, among them the principle of socio-cultural partnership and its theoretical analysis in formulating the socio-cultural meanings of the new pedagogical education;
- the substantive justification of the concept of "socially active school" and "socially oriented education";
- the substantive foundations analysis of the future teacher professional competence.

Research methods

The following research methods were used: dynamic and contextual analysis of the educational system, regulatory documents, theoretical analysis of scientific literature, pedagogical observation, assessment. Further, it seems appropriate to focus on methodological approaches to the organization of socio-cultural interaction based on the principle of socio-cultural partnership and suggest the following methodological approaches to solving the formulated problem.

Methodology

The following socio-cultural values have been identified over the course of culturological research:

1. The culture of the student as a free, will-expressing and self-determining personality, who is in

ongoing dialogue with himself, other personalities and works of art give rise to a true culture.

2. The process of General cultural and socio-cultural education, self-education of the individual at different stages and in different conditions of life, to meet the cultural needs of the person.

3. The process of formation of the General and professional culture of the person, activity of various society institutions for these purposes.

4. Communication culture, behavior, relationship of people in society, and also values of life and leisure culture, social environment and professional culture.

5. Values of political, legal, economic, environmental, physical, moral, artistic, aesthetic, psychological and pedagogical culture of the individual.

Humanitarian and culturalological aspect allows to combine in the educational process the General cultural, special and psychological-pedagogical components into the same context. The humanitarian-culturalological approach is based on the principle "from the educated person to the person of culture ", which is focused on the analysis of the subject and extra subject content from the position of the individuals holistic culture.

The results

Analysis of the subject and extra subject content of the modern Pedagogical University (State University of Humanities and Technology) activities allows us to emphasize that higher pedagogical education at the present stage meets the need for designing of the future teacher competence model, which is now being implemented in terms of enhancing the interaction of the state and society, and as mentioned above, can satisfy not only the order of the state to education, but also take into account the educational and social needs of stakeholders – individual citizens, schools, business, public and private organizations, i.e., all subjects involved in the sphere of the educational organization activity, which, at the same time, may differ from each other in type and degree of participation in educational activities, often have different, sometimes even conflicting interests and needs, but are united by a common idea – the idea of creating conceptually priority prospects for the use of social potential in the sphere of modern educational policy. Hence, an important socio - cultural component of the formation of the future teacher competence model is the implementation of the University educational process, focused on the transition to the competence model of the University graduate, in demand for socially – oriented education, modern professional labor market, socially active school (Aldoshina & Grishina, 2017).

Two interrelated components are quite clearly traced in the activity of the SAS - social and educational, allowing the SAS to solve social and educational problems equally successfully and in unbreakable unity. The educational component of the SAS allows to bring education closer to the daily life of the child, as well as to use the resources of the community to solve the problems of younger generation education and training, for the functioning and development of the school. The social component is aimed at encouraging and implementing initiatives to ensure the creation of conditions for building of civil society in Russia, democratization of different social life spheres, to transform schools in the most important resource of functioning and development of the community. The optimal model of SAS, according to the participants of the SAS movement, includes three basic components: the democratization of the school, the partnership of the school and the community, volunteerism.

The school's reconsideration of its educational task, role and status, the development of technologies for interaction with the community allows it to become an open system, a common social and educational space or a social "school-community", creating additional opportunities for attracting new

resources, consolidating, socializing processes and practices, bringing education and training closer to the real life of children, strengthening the socio — cultural orientation of education.

As for the socially-oriented education, the attempt to identify its essence, content, characteristic features in Russia is carried out in those conditions when it is phenomenologically present, but theoretically not yet fully justified, categorically undefined, and, accordingly, conceptually not yet precisely formulated.

But at the same time, Russian socially – oriented education, in contrast to foreign models, is a more complex system aimed at the interaction of the school and the community in a broader context, a system that operates and develops in the unique modern socio-cultural conditions. It seems that today there is an objective necessity to consider SOE not only as a philosophical concept, but also as a social system, a social phenomenon, and finally as a social institution. So what competences should possess a graduate of the Pedagogical University starting the implementation of self-educational activities in the community of socially active school in terms of public - oriented education?

In our opinion as the foundation "topography of the teacher professional competence" will be examined by the professional standard of pedagogical activity (Education in the Russian Federation, 2014), which provides for a different qualitative level of the teacher basic competencies of development:

- * competence in the field of personal qualities,
- * competence in setting goals and objectives of pedagogical activity,
- * competence in motivating students (pupils) to carry out educational activities,
- * competence in the development of activities and pedagogical decision-making program,
- * competence in providing information basis for pedagogical activity,
- * competence in the organization of pedagogical activity.

Together, the named competencies create a system of the teacher basic competencies, which should provide the system of Russian education a worthy place in the top ten world leaders.

The theme of formation of the teacher professional competence is the key in the Professional standard "Teacher" (Professional standard "Teacher"), which is created to establish unified requirements for the content and quality of professional teaching activities, to assess the level of teachers qualification. This document is a normative basis for the new generation teachers training. The idea laid down in the standard is characterized by a fundamental novelty – this is what the current situation of the educational system in Russia requires. Professional standard "Teacher" as a strategic standard of modern educational policy determines the professional requirements for the personality of the teacher, made to implement relevant ideas and regulations, to fully meet social requirements and expectations for teaching staff in the modern socio-cultural situation.

It is the fulfillment of the named conditions that will allow to implement the key provisions of the professional standard "Teacher", aimed at:

- implementation of professional orientation on the future teacher ability to apply psychological and pedagogical technologies (including inclusive), necessity to work with different students: gifted children, socially vulnerable children, children in difficult life situations, migrant children, orphans, children with special educational needs, children with disabilities, children with behavioral deviations, children with addiction, etc.);

- formation and development of universal educational actions, samples and values of social behavior, skills of behavior in the world of virtual reality and social networks, skills of multicultural communication and tolerance, key competences according to international norms, etc.;

- formation of knowledge about the General laws of development and manifestation of personal properties, psychological laws of periodization and crises of age peculiarities of students development;
- formation of skills to organize a psychologically safe and comfortable educational environment, to prevent various forms of violence in school, etc.

It is impossible in the context of the stated problem study not to mention the key competencies of the 21st century citizen: communication skills, cooperation, unconventional thinking, confidence, initiative, etc. these competencies are formed in the Pedagogical University and improved in the socially active school.

It seems appropriate to further illustrate the above mentioned facts with the provisions of the professional standard "Teacher", which specify the personal qualities and professional competence, in particular, communicative, managerial and methodological, necessary for the teacher to implement socio-cultural interaction with the subjects of educational relations in a socially active school, primarily with the parents of students:

* "The ability to form adult- children communities. Knowledge of their social and psychological characteristics and patterns of development" aims teachers at professional orientation and creation of functioning groups, members of which are people of very different ages, primarily participants in educational relations-students and their parents. The main thing at the same time, the teacher's ability to establish a communicative relationship, which is quite difficult. In such groups, it is necessary to ensure a trusting relationship between parents and children, children and teachers, teachers and parents. In achieving the above mentioned goals, communicative competence plays a dominant role.

* "Knowledge of the basic laws of family relations allows to work effectively with the parent community", ensures the effectiveness of the teacher's interaction with the parent community, which correlates with the level of formation of the teacher communicative competence.

* "The ability to support the constructive educational efforts of parents (persons in Loco parentis), students, to involve the family in the issues of child rearing", allows you to have a trusting relationship with the parents of students and have maximum awareness of the educational family environment quality in order to act together.

Next, we highlight the labor actions of the teacher, among which are the following:

* Determination together with the student, his parents (legal representatives), other participants in the educational process (teacher-psychologist, teacher-defectologist, methodologist, etc.), zone of its nearest development and implementation (if necessary) of an individual educational route and individual development program of students guarantees the implementation of individual approaches to students.

* Development (together with other specialists) and implementation together with parents (legal representatives) of child's individual development programs predetermines priorities of personality - oriented education.

As the necessary skills of a teacher, the Professional standard formulates the following:

- * To form child-adult communities.
 - To create training groups (class, club, clubs, etc.) uneven-aged children and adult community learners, their parents (or legal guardians) and teachers.
- * To cooperate with other teaching staff and other specialists in solving educational problems.
- * To manage training groups in order to involve students in the process of training and education, motivating their educational and cognitive activity

The necessity of required knowledge, including:

* Theory and methods of educational systems management.

As it can be seen, in the Provisions of the Professional standard there is a consideration of the real orientations in the subjects of education, and, of course, adequate consideration of their socio - cultural needs.

Questions for discussion

Pedagogical Universities are aimed at training personnel for social active society that meet the requirements, which initiate a modern school to improve its own mission: educational tasks, role and status.

It is a socially active school that will become the model that meets the socio-cultural needs of all subjects of education. Therefore, the problem of qualitative changes in the modern teacher training at a Pedagogical University, formed to search for new solutions and socio-cultural opportunities for training a new teacher, taking into account international experience and in accordance with new challenges, is increasingly becoming the subject of public and professional discussions (Skudareva & Osinina, 2017).

However, building the University educational process on the basis of competence is currently quite a complex problem, because the main educational program today is created to integrate a set of higher education initiatives in the system, ensuring the implementation of the requirements of all stakeholders, members of the community: students, parents and teachers, employers, individuals, schools, business, public and private organizations, and, of course, the state.

At the same time, attention to the socio-cultural partnership is now evident; it is one of the conditions for the development of open educational systems and an effective mechanism for involving a wide range of stakeholders in the discussion and solution of socio-cultural problems of education development. The tasks determined by the doctrine of education development and modernization are aimed at ensuring the openness of the education system to various influences from society and the state, involving them in the solution of educational tactics and strategy issues.

The formulated thesis can also be conditioned by the fact that the organization in practice of such partnership type is not systematic enough, reducing the effectiveness of the socially significant problem solution (in particular, the active interaction of the state and society). At the same time, the algorithm of building a socio-cultural partnership as a principle of socio-cultural interaction between the state and society in the process of future teacher professional training is not sufficiently developed.

Unfortunately, so far contemporary educational practice is such that outdated teaching methods and technologies in a pedagogical university, low practice-oriented basic educational programs of higher education, their isolation from the realities of general education, weak involvement of employers in the university educational process hamper the development of new pedagogical education. The target set is the development of a multi-component model of pedagogical education with the involvement of all kinds of resources: infrastructural, organizational and managerial, personnel, content, educational, methodological, etc., which will provide a new technological organization of the educational process, the digitization of the educational environment, a radical change in the content and organizational components of education, socio-cultural environment, intergenerational, multicultural communication of education subjects.

Conclusion

Based on the above, the conclusion considers that the professional level of the future teacher

readiness to work in the new conditions directly depends on the university where he studied, his resource capabilities and innovative potential. It becomes obvious that a pedagogical university today is not just an object passively reacting on external challenges, but a source of new education, in other words, it is the center for creating an innovation space for which socio-cultural development is an internal task.

The presented data are the results of long-term scientific research and study of the practice in a multi-level regional education system. The confirmation of the wide possibilities of the socio-cultural partnership as a mechanism of socio-cultural interaction of the state and society and their subjects, among which the main is the socially active school in a socially-oriented education are very significant. A new look at the problem broadens the theoretical idea of the professional training of the teacher of the future in the contemporary situation of Russian education development and stimulates projecting new pedagogical education with wide variety of resources: infrastructural, organizational, managerial, personnel, content, educational and methodical, etc., aimed at solving the strategic tasks of modern professional pedagogical education of new socio-cultural meanings.

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